

Analysis of Brick Masonry Infill Frame with Opening Using ANN

Dinesh Kumar Gupta^{1*}, Raghavendra Yadav²

¹ Department of Civil Engineering, Institute of Engineering, Tribhuvan University, Nepal

² Department of Civil Engineering, Everest Engineering College, Pokhara University, Nepal

Accepted November 17,2021

Published November 30,2022

*Corresponding Author:

Dinesh Kumar Gupta,
replydinesh@ioe.edu.np

DOI :<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5918778>

Pages: 239-247

Funding: None

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):

Gupta, D. K., & Yadav, R. (2021). Analysis of Brick Masonry Infill Frame with Opening Using ANN. *North American Academic Research*, 4(11), 239-247. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5918778>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The FEM Models normally consume lots of human effort and time to consider all the effecting factors such as non-linear behavior of the infill materials, lack of fit, non-homogeneity of the materials, etc. The tentative design parameters can be predicted using the Artificial Intelligence and this computing power of the modern-day computers has been used extensively in modern era to fulfill the intended purpose. The computer is trained with the data sets generated from the simulation of the infill-frame structure done in sophisticated software capable of non-linear analysis (ANSYS). The trained Artificial Neural Network is used for the validation of the data. The results of the test set of data obtained from the trained ANN compared with results obtained from software exhibited errors from 0.65% to 13.33%.

Keywords: INFILL FRAME, ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK, ANSYS, NON-LINEAR BEHAVIOR, FEM, BRICK MASONRY

Introduction

Infill panels are widely used as interior partitions and external walls in buildings, but they are usually treated as non-structural elements and not included in the design. They are assumed to constitute a second line of defense over bare frame. Specifically, the variability of the mechanical properties of infill panels, depending on both the mechanical properties of their materials and the construction details, introduces difficulty in predicting the behavior of infill panels. The overall geometry i.e. number of bays and stories, aspect ratio of infill panels, and the location and the dimensions of openings play also an important role in the evaluation of the strength and stiffness of the infill panels. Results from these analyses of flexible skeletal structures can be radically away from actual situations. The computing capabilities of the computers can be used to deal with the problems imposed due to the inconsistent characteristics of the infill.

Figure 1-1: Frames with and without the infill

The demand for inelastic design is increasing on daily basis with the advancement of computational technology and ever-increasing trend of research activities. The models which can account for nonlinear behavior of individual materials becomes more appropriate in the context. During early days, computational challenges and efforts to be put for simulation compelled people to accept the state of linear assumption. Now, the advancement in computational technology stipulates more precise computational techniques, which can minimize the gap between realistic value and the approximation.

Structural design is an iterative process [Simonen 2014]. The initial design is the first step in design process. The structural engineer has to exercise caution and use his judgement, experience, knowledge in addition to calculations in the interpretation of the codal provisions to obtain an efficient and economic design. The analysis of the structure is then carried out using initial design. Based on the results of the analysis, a re-design of the structure is carried out. The efficiency of the design process depends heavily on initial presumption. A good initial design reduces the number of subsequent analysis–design cycles. This phase is extremely difficult to computerize as it needs human intuition.

In recent years’, efforts have been made to computerize the initial design process using artificial neural networks as they can learn from available designs during training process. They are based on quite simple principles but take advantage of their mathematical nature in terms of non-linear iteration. One of the tools that can be an extremely powerful for the prediction of subsequent design parameters is Neural Networks with Back Propagation (BP) learning [Shakya 2003].

The origins of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are in the field biology. The biological brain consists of billions of highly interconnected neurons forming a neural network. With regards to information processing, neural networks can easily exploit the massively parallel local processing and distributed storage properties in the brain. ANN is an informational system simulating the ability of a biological neural network by interconnecting many simple neurons (Fig. 1-2). The neuron accepts inputs from a single or multiple source and produces outputs by simple calculations, processing with a predetermined non-linear function. Therefore, the primary characteristics of an ANN can be presented as following: (1) the ability of learning; (2) distributed memory; (3) fault tolerance and (4) operating in parallel.

Figure 1-2: Structure of Artificial Neural Network Model

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

Three different materials viz., reinforced concrete, brick and mortar are used for modeling to incorporate the complex heterogeneity involved in the infills as far as possible [Pradhan 2009]. Two types of brick are considered, viz Machine-made Brick (MB) and Local Brick (LB). Similarly, two compositions of mortar based on their cement/sand (C:S) ratio are also considered. The link elements being used are also modeled using the material for the reinforced concrete. The area for the link element is computed using average spacing of the link elements throughout the run of the infill and the thickness of the beam and column element. The material non-linearity of all the materials is also considered. An overview of the material properties used for the analysis purpose is presented in the tabular form below.

Table 2-1: Material properties used in analysis

Material	Remarks	Modulus of Elasticity E (N/m ²)	Poisson's Ratio	Density (kg/m ³)
Reinforced Concrete	General	2.549E+10	0.15	2500
Brick	MB	3.022E+09	0.09	1700
	LB	2.387E+09		
Mortar	1:4	3.651E+09	0.17	1780
	1:6	2.616E+09		

Figure 2-1: Stress-Strain characteristics of Bricks used.

Figure 2-2: Stress-Strain Characteristics of Mortar used

Figure 3-3: Stress-Strain Characteristics of Reinforced Concrete

The afore-mentioned materials and geometries are combined to generate the models which ensured the combination of materials in a systematic way and thus creating the desired variation in the analysis that is intended to be given to this research. A single-bay single-story, single-sized central-opening with varying span is considered for the study and their lateral stiffness is determined by non-linear analysis considering material non-linearity. The single-bay single-story infill frame considered is shown in figure 3-4. Central opening of width 1500 mm by 1800 mm height is considered for the case. The 200 data sets comprised of variation of single height, five spans, two brick-types, two mortar-types, two thicknesses of infill and five loads applied at top left corner thus making a total of $5 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 5 = 200$ models to be analyzed. ANSYS was used for the research which is capable of non-linear analysis.

Figure 3-4: Sample model prepared for the analysis

The non-linear analysis results from ANSYS are taken as the reference for the preparation of the training sets. NeuNet Pro, a complete neural network development system, is used in this study to prepare the sets. The graphical user interface incorporated in the software makes it extremely easy to operate and handle while providing flexibility in operation and handling as well. Another 16 data sets were also prepared using ANSYS, but this time for the validating purpose.

Table 2-2: Parametric characteristics of infilled frames analyzed

Analyses	Aspect Ratios	Opening (%)	Brick	Mortar	Wall thickness(mm)	Lateral load (KN)	
1 – 40	1.0	30	Machine Made Brick	1:4	110	100,200,300,400,500	
					230		
				1:6	110		
					230		
			Local Brick	1:4	110		100,200,300,400,500
					230		
				1:6	110		
					230		
41 - 80	0.85	25.7	Same as in 1 - 40				
81 – 120	0.75	22.5	Same as in 1 - 40				
121 – 160	0.67	20	Same as in 1 - 40				
161 – 200	0.6	18	Same as in 1 - 40				

Results

The responses are observed with respect to variation in Wall thickness, Aspect Ratios, Bricks and Mortar. The variation in stiffness with % of opening is as shown in the figure

Figure 3-1: variation of stiffness with opening %

In the graphs shown below, the individual blocks show the displacement for a particular span and the colors within indicate the displacement difference for one hundred kilo-Newton loads, i.e., the lowermost color give the displacement value for hundred kilo-Newton load and the color right above the lowermost color gives the value of the displacement difference of two hundred load and one hundred loads.

Figure 3-2: variation of displacement with span

The graphs below show that the value of stiffness for 230mm thick wall is greater than those compared to 110mm thick walls and also the stiffness is maximum for hundred kilo-newton load and minimum for five

hundred kilo-Newton loads. Also, the best combination of the masonry units taken in this research comes to be the one with 230mm thick wall, machine made brick and with 1:4 mortar specification.

Figure 3-2: variation of stiffness with load

In order to evaluate the effective widths of the equivalent diagonal strut for the walls in the infill frames analyzed, it is hereby assumed that the equivalent diagonal strut is pinned to the intersection of the beams and columns at the loaded corners; the modulus of elasticity and the thickness of the strut are the same as those of the wall; and the frame connections are rigid. In Table 3-1 effective widths derived from the finite element analyses of rigidly connected infilled frames with 110 mm thick walls are compared with effective widths calculated from some of the standard expressions [Angel & Abrams 1994, FEMA 306 1998, FEMA 356 1998 and Mainstone 1971]. The finite element (FE) effective widths are determined by replacing the infill wall with a strut [Mondal and Jain 2008] that results in the same infill frame stiffness as from the corresponding finite element analysis.

Table 3-1: Comparison of strut widths

Aspect Ratio	Model Designation	FEM	FEMA		Mainstone		Angel et al.	
		W_{ds} (m)	W_{ds} (m)	Factor of FE	W_{ds} (m)	Factor of FE	W_{ds} (m)	Factor of FE
1	MB4	0.141	0.115	0.817	0.081	0.572	0.091	0.647
	MB6	0.145	0.117	0.807	0.082	0.563	0.091	0.629

	LB4	0.144	0.116	0.809	0.081	0.565	0.091	0.634
	LB6	0.148	0.118	0.800	0.082	0.557	0.091	0.617
0.86	MB4	0.161	0.143	0.886	0.100	0.621	0.113	0.703
	MB6	0.165	0.145	0.879	0.101	0.614	0.113	0.686
	LB4	0.164	0.144	0.880	0.101	0.615	0.113	0.690
	LB6	0.171	0.147	0.859	0.102	0.598	0.113	0.662
0.75	MB4	0.205	0.177	0.862	0.124	0.603	0.139	0.677
	MB6	0.211	0.180	0.852	0.125	0.593	0.139	0.658
	LB4	0.208	0.179	0.860	0.125	0.599	0.139	0.667
	LB6	0.215	0.182	0.846	0.126	0.587	0.139	0.646
0.67	MB4	0.238	0.214	0.901	0.149	0.628	0.166	0.699
	MB6	0.241	0.218	0.905	0.151	0.628	0.166	0.690
	LB4	0.239	0.217	0.908	0.151	0.631	0.166	0.696
	LB6	0.246	0.221	0.897	0.153	0.621	0.166	0.676
0.6	MB4	0.291	0.255	0.875	0.177	0.608	0.195	0.670
	MB6	0.295	0.259	0.878	0.179	0.607	0.195	0.661
	LB4	0.293	0.258	0.879	0.178	0.609	0.195	0.665
	LB6	0.302	0.262	0.868	0.181	0.598	0.195	0.646

The 200 data sets were fed into the network and trained to produce a single output from the network at a time. After the training of the network is done, the predicted output is compared with the standard outputs obtained from the analysis done in ANSYS. The corresponding maximum error is noted down. A sample error comparison chart for the displacement-output is shown as below. The dots show the predicted data and the diagonal line corresponds to the actual data.

Figure 3-3: Comparison of actual versus predicted data

Conclusion

The responses from the non-linear analysis of the infill model prepared in ANSYS were used as training data sets. Standard Neural Network software was used to train the network and later some data sets were used for validation of the results predicted. Neural network can be extremely useful in predicting the pattern in the mass data and at the same time it can be used for the quick prediction of the desired field, for which it has to be trained previously. A typical neural network fed into 200 data sets as training data set with just one hidden layer containing 5 nodes produced accuracy as high as 99.35%. The results obtained from trained ANN, in comparison to those obtained from test set, were found to be satisfactory with error ranging from 0.65% minimum to 13.33% maximum.

References

1. Angel, R. and D.P. Abrams, 1994. Out-of-plane strength evaluation of URM infill panels, Proceedings of the NCEER Workshop on Seismic Response of Masonry Infills, (RMI' 94), Technical Report NCEER-94-0004, pp: 1/9-14, 1994.
2. FEMA 306, Evaluation of Earthquake Damaged Concrete and Masonry Wall Buildings, Basic Procedures Manual, prepared by: Applied Technology Council (ATC-43 Project) 555 Twin Dolphin Drive, Suite 550, Redwood City, California 94065, Prepared for: The Partnership for Response and Recovery, Washington, D.C., Funded by: Federal Emergency Management Agency, 1998
3. FEMA 356, Prestandard and commentary for the seismic rehabilitation of the buildings, prepared by: American society of Civil Engineers (ASCE), Reston, Virginia, Prepared for: Federal Emergency Management Agency, Washington, D.C., 1998
4. Mainstone, R.J., Stiffnesses and strengths of infilled frames. Proc. Instit. Civil Eng., 49: 230-263,1971.
5. Mondal, G. and Jain, S.K., Lateral Stiffness of Masonry Infilled Reinforced Concrete (RC) Frames with Central Opening, Earthquake Spectra, Volume 24, No. 3, pages 701–723, August 2008
6. Pradhan, P.L., Composite Actions of Brick Infill Wall in RC Frame under In-Plane Lateral Load, Institute of Engineering, Tribhuvan University, Ph. D. Thesis, 2009
7. Shakya, A., Application of Artificial Neural Network in the Analysis of In-filled Frame., Institute of Engineering, Tribhuvan University, M. Sc. Thesis,2003
8. Simonen, K., Iterating Structures: Teaching Engineering as Design, Journal of Architecture Engineering, Vol. 20, Issue 3, 2014.

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.

